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Review Article: Novel Approach for Colon Targeted Drug Delivery

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ABSTRACT

Colonic drug absorption, as an alternative to parenteral drug delivery, is evaluated for its potential advantages and limitations. Methodologies for studying and enhancing colonic drug absorption are discussed with emphasis on the biological and chemical nature of absorption barriers. Recent efforts at identifying factors that control colonic drug absorption and which might be exploited in a delivery scheme are described. Although oral delivery has become a widely accepted route of administration of therapeutic drugs, the gastrointestinal tract presents several formidable barriers to drug delivery. The delivery of drugs to the colon has a number of therapeutic implications in the field of drug delivery. In the recent times, the colon specific delivery systems are also gaining importance not only for local drug delivery of drugs but also for the systemic delivery of protein and peptide drugs. The various approaches that can be exploited to target the release of drug to colon include prodrug formation, coating with Ph sensitive polymers, coating with biodegradable polymers, embedding in biodegradable matrices, hydrogel, timed release systems, osmotic and bioadhesive systems. Solid formulations intended for targeted drug release into the lower gastrointestinal (GI) tract are beneficial for the localized treatment of several diseases and conditions, mainly inflammatory bowel diseases, irritable bowel syndrome and colon cancer. Also, because of their inherent potential to delay or avoid systemic drug absorption from the small intestine, colonic formulations can be utilized for chronotherapy of diseases which are affected by circadian biorhythms (e.g., asthma, hypertension and arthritis), and to achieve clinically relevant bioavailability of drugs that are poorly absorbed from the upper parts of the GI tract because of their polar nature and/or susceptibility to chemical and enzymatic degradation in the small intestine (e.g., proteins and peptides).

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INTRODUCTION

By definition, colonic delivery refers to targeted delivery of drugs into the lower GI tract, which occurs primarily in the large intestine (i.e., colon). Targeted delivery of drugs to the colon has attracted much interest recently for local treatment of variety of colonic diseases such as irritable bowel syndrome (IBS), colorectal cancer, and inflammatory bowel diseases (IBD), which includes both ulcerative colitis and Crohn's disease. Apart from these local treatment, the colon is used for the systemic absorption of proteins and peptides and also for those drugs where a delay in drug absorption is required from a therapeutic point of view.¹

Specific targeting of drugs to the colon is recognized to have several therapeutic advantages. Drugs, which are destroyed by the stomach acid and / or metabolized by pancreatic enzymes, are slightly affected in the colon, and sustained colonic release of drugs can be useful in the treatment of nocturnal asthma, angina and arthritis. Treatment of colonic diseases such as ulcerative colitis, colorectal cancer and Crohn's disease is more effective with direct delivery of drugs to the affected area. Likewise, colonic delivery of vermicides and colonic diagnostic agents require smaller doses.²

In the past few years many colon-specific dosage forms have been developed, including prodrugs, cross-linked hydrogels, matrices, and coated dosage forms. Coated dosage forms are preferred because of innovations in the coating technology and wide flexibility in the design. These coated dosage forms are mainly based upon one of the following:

- The pH-controlled release coatings that are insoluble at the lower pH of the stomach and dissolve in the lumen of the small intestine. To achieve release in the colon, the start of the drug release is controlled by increasing the thickness of the coating, allowing a pH- and time controlled polymer

dissolution and drug release. These pH-sensitive enteric polymers dissolve in a pH between 6 and 7 and thus release the drug as soon as the pH of the intestine reaches 6 or 7. Some of these enteric polymers are cellulose acetate phthalate, HPMC phthalate, and Eudragit L and S.

- 1 Time-controlled release coating in which the lag time depends upon coating thickness and drug release can be accomplished by changes in osmotic pressure or disruption of the coating by swelling of the core.³

Need of colon targeted drug delivery.⁴

- Targeted drug delivery to the colon would ensure direct treatment at the disease site, lower dosing and fewer systemic side effects.
- Site-specific or targeted drug delivery system would allow oral administration of peptide and protein drugs, colon-specific formulation could also be used to prolong the drug delivery.
- Colon-specific drug delivery system is considered to be beneficial in the treatment of colon diseases.
- The colon is a site where both local or systemic drug delivery could be achieved, topical treatment of inflammatory bowel disease, e.g. ulcerative colitis or Crohn's disease. Such inflammatory conditions are usually treated with glucocorticoids and sulphasalazine (targeted).
- A number of others serious diseases of the colon, e.g. colorectal cancer, might also be capable of being treated more effectively if drugs were targeted to the colon.
- Formulations for colonic delivery are also suitable for delivery of drugs which are polar and/or susceptible to chemical and enzymatic degradation in the upper GI tract, highly affected by hepatic metabolism, in particular, therapeutic proteins and peptides.

Advantages and Disadvantages of Colonic Drug Delivery System.⁵

Advantages	1.1.1 Disadvantages
Reduced dose frequency	1.1.2 Low dose loading
1.1.3 Improved patient compliance	Higher need of excipients
Delivery of drug in its intact form as close as possible to the target sites.	Lack of manufacturing Reproducibility and efficacy
1.1.4 Reduction in dose size	Multiple formulation steps
Improve bioavailability	Large number of process variables
1.1.5 Flexibility in design	Need of advanced technology.
Reduced incidence of adverse side effects improved tolerability.	Skilled personal needed for Manufacturing of colonic drug delivery system
Protection of mucosa from irritating drugs.	-----
Drug loss is prevented by extensive first pass metabolism.	-----
Lower daily cost to patient due to fewer dosage units are required by the patient.	1.1.6 -----

Limitations and Challenges in Colon Targeted Drug Delivery.⁴

- I.** One challenge in the development of colon-specific drug delivery systems is to establish an appropriate dissolution testing method to evaluate the designed system in-vitro. This is due to the rationale after a colon specific drug delivery system is quite diverse.
- II.** As a site for drug delivery, the colon offers a near neutral pH, reduced digestive enzymatic activity, a long transit time and increased responsiveness to absorption enhancers; however, the targeting of drugs to the colon is very complicated. Due to its location in the distal part of the alimentary canal, the colon is particularly difficult to access. In addition to that the wide range of pH values and different enzymes present throughout the

gastrointestinal tract, through which the dosage form has to travel before reaching the target site, further complicate the reliability and delivery efficiency.

- III.** Successful delivery through this site also requires the drug to be in solution form before it arrives in the colon or alternatively, it should dissolve in the luminal fluids of the colon, but this can be a limiting factor for poorly soluble drugs as the fluid content in the colon is much lower and it is more viscous than in the upper part of the GI tract.

In addition, the stability of the drug is also a concern and must be taken into consideration while designing the delivery system. The drug may potentially bind in a nonspecific way to dietary residues, intestinal secretions, mucus or faecal matter. The resident microflora could also affect colonic performance via

metabolic degradation of the drug. Lower surface area and relative 'tightness' of the tight junctions in the colon can also restrict drug transport across the mucosa and into the systemic circulation. Colon Anatomy.⁶ The GI tract is divided into stomach, small intestine and large intestine. The large intestine extending from the ileocecal junction to the anus is divided in to three main parts. These are the colon, the rectum and anal canal. The entire colon is about 5 feet (150 cm) long, and is divided in to five major segments. Peritoneal folds called as mesentery which is supported by ascending and descending colon. The right colon consists of the cecum, ascending colon, hepatic flexure and the right half of the transverse colon and the values were shown in Table 1. The left colon contain the left half of the transverse colon, descending colon, splenic flexure and sigmoid. The rectum is the last anatomic segment before the anus. The human intestine and colon were shown in Figure 1 and Figure 2 respectively. The major function of the colon is the creation of suitable environment for the growth of colonic microorganisms, storage reservoir of faecal contents, expulsion of the contents of the colon at an appropriate time and absorption of potassium and water from the lumen. The absorptive capacity is very high, each about 2000ml of fluid enters the colon through the ileocecal valve from which more than 90% of the fluid is absorbed. On average, it has been estimated that colon contains only about 220 gm of wet material equivalent to just 35 gm of dry matter. The majority of this dry matter is bacteria. The colon tissue containing the villi, lymph, muscle, nerves, and vessels.

pH differences in the colon

On entry in to the colon, the pH dropped to 6.4 ± 0.5 . The pH in the mid colon was found to be 6.6 ± 1 and in the left colon, 7.0 ± 1 and the values are shown in Table 2.

Figure 1: Structure of human intestine

Figure 2: Structure of colon

Table 1: Measures of different parts of colon

Sr.NO	Large Intestine	Length(cm)
1	Cecum	6-9
2	Ascending colon	20-25
3	Descending colon	10-15
4	Transverse colon	40-45
5	Sigmoid colon	35- 40
6	Rectum	12
7	Anal canal	3

Table 2: Average pH of the GI Tract

Location	pH
1. Stomach	1.5 – 2.0
Fasted condition	3.0 – 5.0
Fed condition	5.0 – 6.5
2. Small intestine	6.0 – 7.5
Jejunum	6.4
Ileum	6.7 – 7.3
3. Large intestine	6.4
Right colon	6.0- 7.6
Mid colon and Left colon	

Table 3: Gastrointestinal Transit time of contents

Organ	Transit Time (hr)
Stomach	<1(fasting)
Small intestine	>3(fed)
Large intestine	3-4

1.1.7 Gastrointestinal transit

Gastric emptying of dosage form is highly variable and depends primarily on whether the subject is fed or fasted and on the properties of the dosage form such as size and density. The transit times of dosage forms in tract are shown in Table 3.

Diseases affecting colonic transit have important implications for drug delivery, diarrhoea increases colonic transit and constipation decreases it. The digestive motility pattern takes place when food is present in the stomach. It is said by regular, frequent contractions (about 4-5/min.) which effect the mixing intestinal contents and moving them towards the colon in short segments and lasts as long as food remains present in the stomach. The most frequent movements seen in the colon are a very slow segmenting movement that typically occurs every 30 minutes.

Colonic microflora.⁷

The human colon is a dynamic and ecologically diverse environment, containing over 400 distinct species of bacteria with a population of 10¹¹ to 10¹² CFU/mL, with Bacteroides, Bifidobacterium, Eubacterium, Lactobacillus, etc greatly outnumbering other species. For example, it was reported that Bacteroides, Bifidobacterium and Eubacterium could constitute as much as over 60% of the total cultivable flora. These bacteria produce a wide spectrum of enzymes that, being reductive and hydrolytic in nature, are actively involved in many processes in the colon, such as carbohydrate and protein fermentation,

bile acid and steroid transformation, metabolism of xenobiotic substances, as well as the activation and destruction of potential mutagenic metabolites. Nitroreductase, azoreductase, N-oxide and sulfoxide reductase are the most extensively investigated reductive enzymes, while glucosidase and glucuronidase are the most extensively studied hydrolytic enzymes. The primary source of nutrition for these anaerobic bacteria is carbohydrates such as non-starch polysaccharides (i.e., dietary fibers) from the intestinal chime. It is well established that non-starch polysaccharides are fermented during transit through the colon and the breakdown in the stomach and small intestine is negligible. Enzymes responsible for the degradation of polysaccharides include α -L-arabinofuranosidase, β -D-fucosidase, β -D-galactosidase, β -D-glucosidase, β -xylosidase, with the

last three enzymes being the most active. Additionally, the composition of colonic bacteria and corresponding enzymes can be influenced by many factors, including age, diet, diseases, medication such as antibiotics, and geographic regions. A unique feature of colon microflora is that the growth and activity of certain specific species, most notably bifidobacteria and lactobacilli, can be selectively stimulated by nondigestible oligosaccharides which are known as prebiotics. It has been demonstrated in healthy human volunteers that consumption of fructooligosaccharides, inulin, lactulose, galactooligosaccharides resulted in a significant increase in numbers of bifidobacteria with or without the decrease in the numbers of bacteroides, clostridium, and fusobacteria in fecal samples.

Colon targeting Diseases, Drugs and Sites.⁸

Target sites	Disease conditions	Drug and active agents
Topical action	Inflammatory Bowel Diseases, Irritable bowel disease and Crohn's disease.	Hydrocortisone, Budesonide, Prednisolone, Sulfasalazine, Olsalazine, Mesalazine, Balsalazide
Local action	Chronic pancreatitis pancreatotomy and cystic fibrosis Colorectal cancer	Digestive enzyme supplements 5-Flourouracil
Systemic action	To prevent gastric irritation To prevent first pass metabolism of orally ingested drugs Oral delivery of peptides Oral delivery of vaccines	NSAIDS Steroids Insulin Typhoid

Drug absorption in the colon.

Drugs are absorbed passively by either paracellular or transcellular route. Transcellular absorption involves the passage of drugs through cells and this is the route most lipophilic drugs takes, where paracellular absorption involves the transport of drug through the tight junction between cells and is the route most hydrophilic drug takes. The colon may not be the best site for drug absorption since the colonic mucosa lacks well defined villi as found in the small intestine. The slower rate of transit in colon lets the drug stay in contact mucosa for a longer period than in small intestine which compensates much lower surface area. The colon contents become more viscous with progressive absorption of water as one travels further through the colon. **Table:-4 Criteria for Selection of Drugs for Colon Specific Drug Delivery Systems:**

Criteria	Nonpeptide drugs	Peptide drugs
Drugs used for local effects in colon against GIT diseases	Diclofenac, Metoprolol	Amylin, Calcitonin
Drugs poorly absorbed from upper GIT	Ibuprofen, Theophylline, Isosorbides	Cyclosporine, Desmopressin
Drugs for colon cancer	Pseudoephedrine	Glucagon, Epoetin
Drugs that degrade in stomach and small intestine	Bromophenaramine, 5-Flourouracil	Gonadorelin, Insulin
Drugs that under go extensive first pass	Nimustine, Bleomycin	Sermorelin, Saloatonin

metabolism

Drugs for targeting 5-Aminosalicylic acid, Prednisolone Vasopressin, urotoilitin

This causes a reduced dissolution rate, slow diffusion of drug through the mucosa. Theoretically, drug absorption can occur along the entire GI tract, while in actuality, most drugs are absorbed in the duodenum and proximal jejunum. Recent studies have shown that some drugs (e.g. Theophylline and Metoprolol) continue to be absorbed in the colon.

Drug candidate for colonic drug delivery.⁹

Drugs which show poor absorption from the stomach or intestine including peptide drugs, are most suitable for colon specific drug delivery systems. Selection of carrier for particular drug candidate depends on the physicochemical nature of the drug as well as the disease for which the system is to be used. The factors such as chemical nature, stability and partition coefficient of the drug and the type of the absorption enhancer chosen influence the carrier selection. Choice of drug carrier depends on the functional groups of the drug molecule. There are several ways in which colon specific drug delivery has been attempted. This includes prodrug formation, coating with pH sensitive polymers, coating with biodegradable polymers, embedding in biodegradable matrices and hydrogel, timed-release systems, osmotic systems, and bioadhesive systems.

Role of Natural Polymers in Colon Drug Targeting.¹⁰

The use of bio degradable polymers holds great promise to achieve targeted drug release to the colon. The family of natural polymers has great appeal to drug delivery as it comprises polymers with a large number of derivatizable groups, a wide range of molecular weights, varying chemical compositions, low toxicity and biodegradability yet high stability. Polysaccharides are promising agents for obtaining colon specific drug delivery system. These natural polymers are strongly appealing to use in a truly colon specific commercially available drug delivery system. The

Table:-5 Polysaccharides obtained from various sources

Polysaccharides from plant source.	from	Starch, Cellulose, Pectin, Locust bean gum.	Amylose, Inulin, Guar gum.
Polysaccharides from animal source.	from	Chondroitin Hyalluronic Acid, Chitosan.	Sulphate, Acid,
Polysaccharides from bacterial source.	from	Dextran, Cyclo Dextrins, Curdlan.	
Polysaccharides from Algae.	from	Alginate.	
Polysaccharides from Fungal.	from	Scleroglucan(sclg).	

Table:-6 Natural polymers and synthetic monomers used in hydrogel fabrication.¹¹

Natural polymers	Synthetic monomers/polymers
Chitosan	Hydroxyethylmethacrylate (HEMA)
Alginate	N-(2-Hydroxy propyl)methacrylate (HPMA)
Fibrin	N-Vinyl-2-pyrrolidone (NVP)
Collagen	N-Isopropylacrylamide (NIPAMM)
Gelatin	Vinyl acetate (VAc)
Hyaluronic acid	Acrylic acid (AA)
Dextran	Methacrylic acid (MAA)
	Polyethylene glycol acrylate/methacrylate (IPEGA/PEGMA)
	Polyethylene glycol diacrylate/dimethacrylate (PEGDA/PEGDMA)

reasons for this are that they are non toxic, easy to work with, and will be FDA approved. Also very important is that they are selectively degraded in the colon.

Newly developed colon-specific drug delivery Systems.¹²

1) Intestinal pressure-controlled colon delivery capsules (PCDCs)

Intestinal pressure-controlled colon delivery capsules (PCDCs), relies on the relatively strong peristaltic waves in the colon that lead to an increased luminal pressure. It consists of a capsular shaped suppositories coated with a water-insoluble polymer, ethyl cellulose (Takaya et al., 1995; Hu et al., 2000a; Shibata et al., 2001). Once taken orally, PCDCs behave like an ethyl cellulose balloon since the suppository base liquefies at body temperature. In the upper GI tract, PCDCs are not directly subjected to the luminal pressures since sufficient fluid is present in the stomach and small intestine. Due to the reabsorption of water in the colon (Debongnie and Phillips, 1978), the viscosity of luminal content increases. As a result, increased intestinal pressures directly affect the system via colonic peristalsis (high-amplitude propagated contractions). In response to the raised pressure, PCDCs rupture and release the drug load in the colon. However, it should be noted that our understanding of this raised pressure phase is very limited. It was reported that in healthy subjects this pressure can be as high as 110 mmHg with duration of 14 s (Bassotti and Gaburri, 1988; Rao et al., 2001). But the activity followed the circadian rhythm, with the occurrence of maximum frequency after waking, meals or with defecation (Rao et al., 2001). Based on limited in vivo evaluation (Hu et al., 1998), it has been demonstrated that the performance of this system appears to be dependent on the capsule size and the thickness of ethyl cellulose coating. Hu et al. used the biomagnetic measurement system (BMS) to estimate the GI transit characteristics of this system in healthy volunteers (Hu et al., 2000b). It was found that the capsule arrived at the ascending colon 4 and 5 h after oral administration in two subjects, while a model drug, caffeine, was first detected in the saliva of the same two subjects 6 and 5 h following oral administration, respectively. This indicated that PCDCs were able to deliver the drug to the colon.

2) CODES technology

CODES is an unique colon-specific drug delivery technology that was designed to avoid the inherent

problems associated with pH- or time-dependent systems (Watanabe et al., 1998; Takemura et al., 2000). The design of CODES exploited the advantages of certain polysaccharides that are only degraded by bacteria available in the colon. This is coupled with a pH-sensitive polymer coating. Since the degradation of polysaccharides occurred only in the colon, this system exhibited the capability to achieve colon delivery consistently and reliably. As schematically presented in Fig. 3, one typical configuration of CODES consists of a core tablet coated with three layers of polymer coatings. The first coating (next to the core tablet) is an acid-soluble polymer (in the present case, Eudragit E was used) and outer coating is enteric with a HPMC barrier layer in between to prevent any possible interactions between the oppositely charged polymers. The core tablet is comprised of the active, one or more polysaccharides and other desirable excipients.

Figure: 3 Schematics of the design of CODES technology. [a = organic acid soluble polymer; b = drug; c = saccharide; d = enteric coating polymer]

The polysaccharides, degradable by enterobacteria to generate organic acid, include mannitol, maltose, stachyose, lactulose, fructo oligosaccharide etc. During its transit through the GI tract, CODES remains intact in the stomach due to the enteric protection, but the enteric and barrier coating will dissolve in the small intestine, where the pH is above 6. Because Eudragit E starts to dissolve at pH-5, the inner Eudragit E coating is only slightly permeable and swellable in small intestine. Upon entry into the colon, the polysaccharide inside the core tablet will dissolve

and diffuse through the coating. The bacteria will enzymatically degrade the polysaccharide into organic acid. This lowers the pH surrounding the system sufficient to effect the dissolution of the acid-soluble coating and subsequent drug release.

3). TARGIT Technology:-¹³

TARGIT technology is designed to exploit the advantageous aspects of colonic delivery systems while minimizing or eliminating the factors that lead to variability. The basis of TARGIT technology is a coated injection-modulated starch capsule; hence a description of the technology may conventionally be divided into the capsule component and the coating.

Starch Capsules:- The starch capsules used in the TARGIT are produced by a proprietary injection-moulding process, which was originally developed by capsugel, but now exclusively licensed to west. In brief a starch based pellet formulation is fed into reciprocating screw of an injection moulding machine. As the starch moves along the screw it is heated and compressed to form a melt. The melted material is fed into moulds, the moulds briefly cooled and the moulded parts ejected. The starch capsule comprises two separately modulated components: a body and a lid. In contrast to conventional hard capsule, the lid is sealed onto the body to form a continuous unit that allows for easy application of coatings. The lid is sealed onto the body by application of a thin layer of water / alcohol solution to the inner rim of the lid at the point of closure of the capsule. This process can be performed manually on a small scale or by automated means on a larger scale.

How TARGIT works.

The blend of pH sensitive polymers used in specifically chosen to start dissolving at a relatively low pH to avoid the potential drawbacks associated with polymers that do not dissolve until a high pH is reached, that is, incomplete or delayed disintegration. For example, the preferred 3:1 mixture of eudragit L 100 and S 100 will start to dissolve when a pH of around 6.3 is reached. Choosing a polymer coating that dissolve at such a pH should avoid the issue of the dosage form

failing to disintegrate, although an appropriate coat thickness to be chosen to ensure that the TARGIT capsule remains intact on its passage through the small intestine. Although the thickness is typically chosen to provide delivery to the terminal ileum and ascending colon region, thicker or thinner coatings can modify the release site of TARGIT distally or proximally, respectively. Due to construction of TARGIT, in which the walls of the starch capsule separate the enteric coating from the capsule contents, dissolution of the coating is essentially independent of capsule fill. This avoids the need to reformulate the coating when changing from one drug component or formulation to another. Dissolution testing of TARGIT is generally performed using a paddle apparatus (USP apparatus 2) paddles set at the speed of 50-100 rpm) with the capsule being weighted by loose-coiled wire shrinkers. The typical dissolution medium is 0.1 M hydrochloric acid for first 2 hours of the test to represent the stomach, after which it is replaced by a medium to represent intestine, for example, pH 6.8 phosphate buffer.

FORMULATION TECHNOLOGIES FOR COLON-SPECIFIC DRUG DELIVERY.¹⁴

In recent years, a large number of solid formulations targeting the lower parts of the GI tract, especially the colon, have been reported. These formulations may be broadly divided into four types, which are:-

- (i) pH-dependent (or delayed-release) system designed to release a drug in response to change in pH,
- (ii) Time-dependent (or timed release) system designed to release a drug after a predetermined time,
- (iii) Microbial-dependent (or microbially controlled) system making use of the abundant enterobacteria in the colon, and
- (iv) Pressure dependent system making use of luminal pressure of the colon. Among these, first three are most widespread formulation technologies being developed for pharmaceutical market.

1) pH-DEPENDENT (OR DELAYED-RELEASE) SYSTEMS

Solid formulations for colonic delivery that are based on pH-dependent drug release mechanism are similar to conventional enteric-coated formulations but they differ in target site for delivery and therefore type of enteric polymers. In contrast to conventional enteric-coated formulations, colonic formulations are designed to deliver drugs to the distal (terminal) ileum and colon, and utilize enteric polymers that have relatively higher threshold pH for dissolution. Most commonly used polymers are derivatives of acrylic acid and cellulose. These polymers have ability to withstand an environment ranging from low pH (~1.2) to neutral pH (~7.5) for several hours. Apparently, it is highly desirable for pH-dependent colonic formulations to maintain their physical and chemical integrity during passage through the stomach and small intestine and reach the large intestine where the coat should disintegrate to release the drug locally. It should be however noted that GI fluids might pass through the coat while the dosage form transits through the small intestine. This could lead to premature drug release in the upper parts of GI tract and as a result loss of therapeutic efficacy may occur.

One approach to overcome this problem is to apply higher coating levels of enteric polymers; however, this also allows influx of GI fluids through the coat, and the thicker coats often rupture under the influence of contractile activity in the stomach. In general, the amount of coating required depends upon the solubility characteristics (solubility, dose/solubility, ratio) of the drug, desired release profile and surface area of the formulation, and composition of the coating solution/dispersion. Coating approach is one of the simplest formulation technologies available for colon-specific delivery. It also offers significant advantage in terms of cost and ease of manufacture. From formulation standpoint, coated dosage forms may be either single-unit system or a multi-particulate system, and each of these may be a single-layer product or a multi-layer product. In case of single-layered products, the coating may be

composed of a single enteric polymer that has a pH-dependent solubility or a mixture of two polymers one of which is pH-dependent while other is pH-independent. On the other hand, in case of multi-layer products, the coating is applied in successive layers which could be either based on two enteric polymers that have different pH-dependent solubility profiles, or two polymers one of which is enteric while other has a pH-independent solubility but permeable to intestinal fluids. In either case, the coating can be applied to a wide variety of solid core formulations such as tablets, capsules, minitables, pellets or granules. When coated pellets or granules are filled into a gelatin capsule or compressed together with conventional excipients in the form of tablets, the formulation is regarded as multi-particulate dosage form. The tablets or capsules containing coated pellets or granules can be further coated with a suitable enteric polymer which may be same or different than that used for coating of pellets or granules.

Modified-release formulations that are based on the combination of a pH-dependent and pH-independent polymer are described in a European patent assigned to Aktiebolaget Hässle. The approach involves coating of an active ingredient (e.g., mesalazine) with a mixture of an anionic acrylic polymer soluble just at pH 5.5 (e.g., Eudragit L) and a cationic acrylic polymer insoluble in water (e.g., Eudragit RS or RL). The quantities of anionic acrylic polymers can range from 10 to 85% while that of pH-independent polymers may vary from 15 to 90%. The blending with one or more polymers having a pH-independent solubility thus prevents the active ingredient from being released too rapidly, once the soluble polymer has reached the optimum pH of solubilization. Eudragit RS (RS100) and RL (RL100) are copolymers of acrylic and methacrylic acid esters, which contain a low level of quaternary ammonium groups. Eudragit RL is composed of 60% by weight methyl methacrylate, 30% by weight ethyl acrylate and 10% by weight 2 trimethylammonioethyl methacrylate chloride. On the other hand, Eudragit RS is composed of 65% by weight methyl methacrylate, 30% by weight

ethyl acrylate and 5% by weight 2-trimethylammonioethyl methacrylate chloride. Both copolymers are insoluble in water but they hydrate in GI fluids independent of pH. Since RS has a lower content of quaternary ammonium groups which are hydrophilic in nature, it displays less water permeability and hydration (or swellability) in comparison with RL.

2) **TIME-CONTROLLED (OR TIME-DEPENDENT) SYSTEMS**

Time-controlled systems are useful for synchronous delivery of a drug either at pre-selected times such that patient receives the drug when needed or at a pre-selected site of the GI tract. These systems are therefore particularly useful in the therapy of diseases, which depend on circadian rhythms. Time-controlled formulations for colonic delivery are also delayed-release formulations in which the delay in delivery of the drug is time-based. In these systems, the site of drug release is decided by the transit time of a formulation in the GI tract, which makes it challenging to develop a formulation in order to achieve a precise drug release in the colon. Ideally, formulations are designed such that the site of delivery (i.e. colon) is not affected by the individual differences in the gastric emptying time, pH of the stomach and small intestine or presence of anaerobic bacteria in the colon. On an average, an orally administered dosage form takes about 3 hrs to travel through the length of the small intestine to the beginning of the colon. Compared to gastric emptying rate, the small intestinal transit time is relatively consistent. In principle, time-controlled systems rely on this consistent small intestinal transit time. The drug release from these systems therefore occurs after a predetermined lag phase, which is precisely programmed by selecting a suitable combination of controlled-release mechanisms. In general, time-controlled formulations for colonic delivery include a pH-dependent (enteric coat) component because the transit of a formulation in the GI tract is largely influenced by the gastric emptying time. Enteric coating is also used for preventing the rapid swelling and disintegration in upper GI tract since

other controlled-release components based on mechanism of swelling (gelling), osmosis or a combination of two are often included in the time-release formulations. The first attempt to develop a time-dependent system for colon delivery was made by Ueda et al. These inventors developed a time-controlled explosion system in which drug release is caused by the explosion of a membrane after a definite time period (defined as “lag times”), which is precisely programmed. The system could be in the form of a bead or granule with a four-layered spherical structure, which consists of a core, a drug, swelling agent (e.g., sodium starch glycolate, carboxymethylcellulose sodium) and an outer membrane of water-insoluble polymer (e.g., ethyl cellulose, Eudragit RL). The penetration of GI fluids through the outer membrane causes the expansion of the swelling agent. The resulting stress due to swelling force leads to destruction of the membrane and subsequent rapid drug release. There are several advantages of this system:

1. The release rate or pattern is minimally influenced by the solubility or dissolution rate of the drug.
2. The release pattern is independent of pH of the dissolution medium.
3. The drug is completely released.

Takada described a similar time-controlled formulation in the form of capsules and bilayered tablets. The release time of the drug from formulations is controlled by disintegration lag-time which depends on the balance between the tolerability and thickness of a water-insoluble membrane and the amount of a swellable excipient such as low substituted hydroxypropyl cellulose (L-HPC) and sodium starch glycolate. The shell of the capsule formulation is made up of ethyl cellulose (EC), approximately 120 μm in thickness, which contains micropores at the bottom of body. The fill material is composed of a solid dispersion formulation of the drug filled into a capsule body also made of EC, and a tablet containing L-HPC made by direct compression. Finally, a cap made up of EC is attached to the body of outer EC capsule (Fig. 4)

Figure:-4 . Time-controlled capsule for colonic delivery

After oral administration, GI fluid permeates through the micropores and causes swelling of swellable excipients. This causes an inner pressure, which pushes the drug container. Then the disintegration of the capsules occurs with the breakdown of the capsule cap. In this regard, the disintegration of timecontrolled capsule is dependent on the balance between the swelling pressure of formulated L-HPC and the strength or tolerability of the EC cap. The bilayered tablets are formulated in four steps. First a tablet is made by compression of L-HPC and lactose or stearic acid (first layer), which is then compressed along with mixture of the drug and crystalline cellulose (second layer). The bilayered tablet is then coated with solution of EC and micropores are formed either mechanically or by laser ray on the first layer. Finally, tablets are sugar coated. Shah et al. described a system in the form of a tablet formulation (patent assigned to Hoffman-La Roche Inc.), which could release the drug consistently in the colon via a time-dependent explosion mechanism. The formulation is comprised of three parts:

- i) A central core containing the drug and swelling excipients
- ii) An inner semi-permeable polymer membrane containing a plasticizer which allows water influx but prevents the outward diffusion of drug and
- iii) An outer enteric-coating which dissolves at or above pH 5.5.

The outer enteric coat keeps the tablet intact until it reaches the small intestine. Upon arrival in the

small intestine, the enteric coat dissolves allowing for GI fluid to diffuse through the semi-permeable membrane into the core. As a result, the core swells during the transit of the tablet through the small intestine. Finally, after a consistent period of 4-6 hrs transit in the small intestine, the swollen core burst the semi-permeable membrane releasing the drug in the colon. Lerner et al. described a time-dependent system in which the core is surrounded by two coating layers. The formulation consists of:-

- (a) Core containing a drug and a suitable core material which is preferably a swellable material
- (d) the drug. The drug is released through these channels.

3) MICROBIALLY-CONTROLLED (OR MICROBIALLY-DEPENDENT) SYSTEMS.

These systems are based on the exploitation of the specific enzymatic activity of the microflora (enterobacteria) present in the colon. The colonic bacteria are predominately anaerobic in nature and secrete enzymes that are capable of metabolizing substrates such as carbohydrates and proteins that escape the digestion in the upper GI tract. Most common mechanisms of microbial activation in the colon are azo-reduction and glycosidic-bond hydrolysis. The first commercial product that is based on the principle of microbial activation in the colon is salicylazosulfapyridine, also known as sulfasalazine. This product is marketed for the therapeutic treatment of ulcerative colitis. It is a prodrug in which 5-aminosalicylic acid (the active moiety) is linked by an azo bond to sulfapyridine (the carrier molecule). The prodrug passes through the upper parts of GI tract intact, but once in the colon, the azo bond is cleaved by azo reductase, liberating the active moiety 5-aminosalicylic acid at the site of inflammation. There are several other commercial examples of prodrug-based formulations that depend on this mechanism of activation in the colon. Examples include olsalazine sodium or azodisalsodium (Dipentum capsules), balsalazide disodium (Colazide and Colazal capsules), and Intestinol (bensalazine or bensalazide). Other prodrugs that are useful in delivering drugs to the colon include glycosides, dextran derivatives, amino acids, polyamino acids and cyclodextrins.

The concept of bioactivation of prodrugs via azo reduction in the colon has led to the development of several novel azopolymers. Formulations based on azo-polymers have an important advantage that they

for water-soluble drugs or a non-swellable material for water-insoluble drugs.

- (b) Coating surrounding the core made up of water-insoluble or relatively water-insoluble materials in which a hydrophilic, water-insoluble, particulate is embedded.

- (c) An outer enteric coating surrounding the middle coating layer. This design allows the slow entry of water or aqueous GI fluids into the device. When the delivery device enters the GI tract, the embedded particulate matter takes up the liquid and swells. The particles eventually form channels interconnecting the outer part of the device to the core containing are relatively stable in the upper GI tract, which is attributed to the resistance of azo bonds to chemical and enzymatic degradation in the stomach and small intestine. However, it has been reported that degradation of the azo polymers by enterobacteria is slow. This is attributed to the hydrophobic nature of the azo-polymers, which renders it difficult for azoreductase to approach the azo bond of these polymers. Another critical disadvantage of azopolymer based systems is that there is always a risk of producing a harmful substance originated in an azo linkage so that the system may be unsuitable for long-term use. To overcome these limitations and toxicity concerns of these synthetic polymers, natural polymers especially glycosidic bond containing materials offer a viable alternative for colonic drug delivery. The glycosidic bond-containing polymers include disaccharides, oligosaccharides, and polysaccharides.

Polysaccharide-based formulations are very common since they can be selectively degraded by a colonic enzyme and are natural polymers with proven final toxicity. These formulations are considered safe because they utilize materials that are taken as dietary fiber. Examples of various polysaccharide carriers are given in the Table 5. Various enzymes that are involved in the degradation of some of these polymers are amylase, chitosanase, pectinase, inulinase, xylanase, dextranase, and galactomannanase. It is important to note that there are also certain limitations associated with use of polysaccharides as drug carriers for colonic delivery. These materials are hydrophilic in nature, which renders them either soluble or prone to swelling in the aqueous environment of the GI tract. An illustrative example is that of calcium pectinate. Edman et al disclosed a pharmaceutical composition containing calcium pectinate as a

major component and a filler such as pectin, dextran, microcrystalline cellulose, or mixture thereof. In this formulation, the calcium pectinate composition is used in the form of a coacervate watersoluble matrix (sodium or potassium pectinate) by exchanging calcium ions with sodium or potassium ions present in the digestive fluid of the upper GI tract. This renders the formulation containing calcium pectinate susceptible to premature disintegration and drug release before it reaches the colon. To overcome these inherent limitations of polysaccharide carriers, several approaches have been suggested which may be either based on the chemical modification of the carrier itself or a suitable strategy in which formulation compositions are modified. Most recent approaches to overcome the limitations of polysaccharides for colonic delivery include development of polysaccharide-based film coated dosage forms. These approaches are capable of controlling the swelling of polysaccharides as well provide mechanical strength to the dosage forms. The film coating composition is generally made up of a polysaccharide in combination with a suitable film forming material. Lee et al. described a composition in which tablets containing the drug were coated with a crosslinked gelatin/pectinate film. Alternatively, a gelatin/pectinate soft capsule filled with a drug is also suggested. The gelatin was employed to enhance the mechanical strength of the formulation. Gelatin forms a complex with calcium pectinate by intermolecular forces including ionic bonding, hydrogen bonding and steric forces.

1) PRESSURE-CONTROLLED SYSTEMS

The digestive processes within the GI tract involve contractile activity of the stomach and peristaltic movements for propulsion of intestinal contents. In the large intestine, the contents are moved from one part to the next, as from the ascending to the transverse colon by forcible peristaltic movements commonly termed as mass peristalsis. These strong peristaltic waves in the colon are of short duration, occurring only three to four times a day. However, they temporarily increase the luminal pressure within the colon, which forms the basis for design

pellet but it has the disadvantage that pellets disintegrate and release the drug in the upper GI tract. It is believed that calcium pectinate, which is insoluble in water, is readily converted to a of pressure-controlled systems. The luminal pressure resulting from peristaltic motion is higher in the colon compared to pressure in the small intestine, which is attributed to the difference in the viscosity of luminal contents. In the stomach and small intestine, contents are fluidic because of abundant water in digestive juices, but in the colon, the viscosity of the content is significantly increased due to reabsorption of water from the lumen and formation of feces. To author's knowledge, there is only one invention related to the development of pressure-controlled system for colonic delivery. This particular delivery system NS, Model drugs used were not specified is in the form of a capsule, which is resistant to the pressures of the upper GI tract but is collapsed in the large intestine due to increased pressure. The capsule shells are fabricated from ethylcellulose and the collapse time of the capsule in the large intestine can be controlled by adjusting the thickness of the capsule shell wall. The preferred thickness of the capsule wall is about 35-60 μm .

Conclusion:-

The colonic region of the gastrointestinal tract has become an increasingly important site for drug

Table :-7. Microbially Degradable Materials Used for Colonic Delivery

Class	Examples
Disaccharides	Lactose, Maltose
Oligosaccharides	Cellobiose, Cyclodextrins, Lactulose, Raffinose, Stachyose
Polysaccharides	Alginates, Amylose, Arabinogalactan, Arabinoxylan, Cellulose, Chitosan, Chondroitin sulfate, Dextran, Galactomannan (guar gum, locust bean gum), Inulin, Karaya gum (Kadaya gum), Laminarin, Pectins, and pectates, Starch, Tragacanth gum, Xanthan gum, Xylan.

Table:-8 Examples of colon targeted formulations based on conventional techniques.¹⁵

Technique employed	Polymer used	(s)	Drug used	
pH dependent	Eudragit L100 and S100		Mesalazine NS	
	Eudragit L100 and S100		Diclofenac sodium and 5-ASA	
	Eudragit L100 and S100		Prednisolone	
	Eudragit S, Eudragit FS, Eudragit P4135 F		Paracetamol	
	Eudragit L 30 D-55 and Eudragit FS 30 D			
	Time dependent	Hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose		Pseudo ephedrine HCl Theophylline
		Hydroxyethyl cellulose,ethyl cellulose, microcrystalline cellulose		Indomethacin NS
		Lactose/ behinic acid		Diltiazem HCl
		Hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose		
		Hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose acetate succinate		
Bacteria dependent/ Polysaccharide Based		Chitosan		Diclofenac sodium
		Pectin		Indomethacin
		Guar gum		Dexamethasone
		Chondroitin sulphate		Indomethacin
		Amylose		5-Acetyl salicylic acid
	Alginates		5- Acetyl salicylic acid	

delivery and absorption. Targeted drug delivery would offer considerable therapeutic benefits to

patients, in terms of both local and systemic treatment. Systems that rely on gastrointestinal pH, transit times or pressure for release are unlikely to function as reliable and effective colon-specific delivery vehicles. Colon specificity is more likely to be achieved with systems that utilise natural materials that are degraded by bacterial enzymes of colonic origin. Colonic drug delivery has several attractive aspects including a prolonged residence time of luminal contents, reduced epithelial enzymatic activity, increased tissue responsiveness to absorption enhancers, and natural absorptive characteristics. To better assess the true potential of colonic drug delivery, a more thorough understanding of the basic biological and physiological functions for this region of the GI tract must be obtained. As well, a more thorough understanding of essential physico-chemical properties of potential drug molecules, particularly for peptides and proteins, as they relate to colonic delivery is required. The challenge is to identify approaches which provide safe, yet effective promotion of colonic drug absorption. At the current rate of research in these areas, it is likely that this level of information may be within our reach in the near future for a few vanguard drug molecules.

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